

A Study of the Influence of Data Normalization on 3D REM Reconstruction Methods

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Abstract—The need for fast and accurate spectrum utilization characterization in three dimensional (3D) space, has been established as a significant topic in modern wireless communications. A critical consideration in this regard, is the reconstruction of radio environment maps (REMs) from a set of measurements, which is ordinarily much smaller than the number of samples necessary to achieve high fidelity. Consequently, 3D interpolation methods are widely utilized. This study compares the performance of established statistical and deep learning (DL) approaches for 3D REM reconstruction for three types of simulated and real-world measured spectrum data. More specifically, the effect of the received signal strength (RSS) range between non-normalized and normalized values, is assessed. Root mean square error (RMSE) of as low as -8 dB is achieved for sampling ratio of 10%. The results establish the normalization of the RSS data improves the accuracy for applications that do not require prediction of the exact RSS values such as identifying areas with under-utilized spectrum.

Index Terms—Deep learning, interpolation, Kriging, radio environment maps, spectrum utilization, volumetric measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

The current research efforts toward the Sixth Generation (6G) wireless networks are focused on both the implementation of seamless information exchange on the ground, in the air and in space, as well as the support of the upcoming applications characterized by increased density and more stringent latency and throughput requirements [1], [2]. Thus, achieving greater spectrum utilization efficiency is crucial, which is dependent on precise spectrum occupancy characterization [1]. A promising approach to realize this functionality is through radio environment maps (REMs) in spatial three-dimensional (3D) space as they provide a practical database

of spectrum usage variations for predictive resource allocation of terrestrial and aerial base stations (BSs) [3], [4]. Building high-fidelity REMs is non-trivial as obtaining the complete set of received signal strength (RSS) measurements is costly and length process even if modern ray tracing simulations are employed [5]. Consequently, the topic of REM reconstruction by interpolating the reduced set of measurements, has been widely studied [6]. The authors of [7], [8] employ a prominent variant of a convolutional neural network (CNN) with skip connections for feature information exchange between the contracting and expansive sections of the model, termed U-Net. It is expanded in the PM-Net [9] by including the dilation operation within the convolutional layers between the network's two sections. These CNNs are used for reconstructing two dimensional (2D) REMs, obtaining a root mean square error (RMSE) of as little as 6 dB for a sampling ratio ρ of 5%, and applied for coverage extension and user association in a terrestrial wireless network [7], [9]. Dilation is also applied for a modified convolutional autoencoder (CAE) [5], termed CAE with dilation (CAED) for 3D REM reconstruction in [10], achieving lower computational complexity and an RMSE of -10 dB for $\rho = 5\%$. Indoor coverage mapping of common television broadcast channels under 1 GHz using 3D REMs for real-world measurements collected using a software-defined radio (SDR) receiver, was performed in [11]. Nearest neighbor (NN), Kriging and inverse distance weighting (IDW) statistical methods are employed, achieving RMSE < 10 dB for $\rho < 30\%$ [3], [4], [12].

This paper builds on prior works by evaluating several prominent 3D REM interpolation methods for three types of datasets - generated, simulation-based (simulated), and real-

world (RW) measurements obtained through SDRs. The first of these is generated via a common method, by sampling a set of large-scale REM according to the procedure described in [10]. The second type is obtained through a simulation of RSS reception by a unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) mounted BS from terrestrial UEs, described in [13]. The third dataset is obtained from real-world measur, reaching the best accurayements that are interpolated to the same grid as described in [10]. The training data is comprised of 3D REMs of the first and second type, while the testing data combines a separate set of examples of all three types. A comparison is made not only in terms of the reconstruction methods but also for the value range of the input RSS samples, to determine the impact of normalization on the accuracy.

The contribution of this work is as follows:

- An empirical validation of statistical and DL methods for 3D REM reconstruction in non-normalized and normalized RSS samples to assess the effect of data normalization. Generated, simulation-based, and real-world measurement data are used. RMSE of as low as -8 dB is achieved for sampling ratio of 10% using the CAED method. The results establish that normalized RSS data improve the accuracy for applications that do not require prediction of the exact RSS values.

II. SUMMARY ON EXPERIMENTS AND EXPERIMENTAL DATASETS

1) Description of the 3D REM Reconstruction Problem:

This Section describes the 3D REM reconstruction problem and the structure of the datasets used for training. The datasets contain RSS measurements at $M_{\mathbb{A}}$ locations that together form the space \mathbb{A} . For each location (i, j, k) , the RSS is defined as $r_{(i,j,k)}$. By combining the measurements for all $M_{\mathbb{A}}$ locations, the tensor of samples $\mathcal{R} = [\mathbf{R}_0, \dots, \mathbf{R}_{M_z-1}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{M_x \times M_y \times M_z}$ is formed, where $\mathbf{R}_k = [r_0, \dots, r_{M_y-1}]^T$, $k \in \{0, \dots, M_z - 1\}$ and $\mathbf{r}_j = [r_0, \dots, r_{M_x-1}]$, $j \in \{0, \dots, M_y - 1\}$, with r_i , $i \in \{0, \dots, M_x - 1\}$ being the measurement sample at position $(i, j = \text{const}, k = \text{const})$. M_x , M_y and M_z denote the number of positions on the x , y , and z axis, respectively. The locations of the recorded measurements form the subset $\mathcal{Z} = \{z_0, z_1, \dots, z_{N_{\mathcal{Z}}-1}\} \subset \mathbb{A}$ with $N_{\mathcal{Z}}$ being the number of locations within \mathcal{Z} , and $N_{\mathcal{Z}} = \rho M_{\mathbb{A}}$, where ρ is the 3D REM's sampling ratio, which denotes the fraction of all points within \mathbb{A} at which measurement samples were collected. For all datasets, both the measurements with non-normalized values of RSS, and those with normalized values (in the range of $[0; 1]$) are considered. The non-normalized levels are represented in non-logarithmic values for the statistical methods, and in dB in the case of DL methods. These different representations are necessary as the statistical methods are more precise for non-logarithmic data as its quantitative properties are different from those of the alternative. On the other hand, DL methods may not achieve convergence if very small numbers (natural for RSS

levels) are considered. The normalization r_i^{norm} of the sample r_i , $i \in \{0, \dots, M_x - 1\}$ is done by:

$$r_i^{norm} = \frac{1}{\left| \frac{r_i}{r_{max}} \right|}, \quad (1)$$

where r_{max} is the largest sample in \mathcal{R} . As the values are in dB (i.e. they are negative, and therefore the absolute values of the high levels are smaller than the absolute values of the low levels), the fraction are reversed to normalize the data in the interval $[0; 1]$.

When it comes to statistical methods, the points considered to have known RSS, and form a subset $\mathcal{C} = \{c_i\}_{i=1}^{N_P}$, $\mathcal{Z} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ of N_P samples is selected, such that $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathbb{Z}$. The unknown points are estimated using the known ones using the statistical interpolation. The Linear, NN, IDW, and Kriging methods are evaluated in this work, using the following calibration parameters: the Linear interpolation scaling coefficient $S_c = \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{R}]$, number $N_z = 5$ of variogram points and smoothness parameter $\nu = 1.55$ (Kriging), and IDW coefficient $\alpha = 1.05$.

For DL methods, a mask tensor $\mathcal{M} \in \{0, 1\}^{M_x \times M_y \times M_z}$ is applied to show which measurement samples within an example tensor will be used as a training/testing data for the estimation of the unknown points. These samples' locations form the subset $\mathcal{Z} \subset \mathbb{A}$ such that $[\mathcal{M}]_{i,j,k} = 1$ if $(i, j, k) \in \mathcal{Z}$, and $[\mathcal{M}]_{i,j,k} = 0$ otherwise. Then, the reduced sampling tensor, also termed *sampled map*, $\Psi^{M_x \times M_y \times M_z \times 2}$ is obtained by concatenating \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{M} along the fourth dimension. The evaluated interpolation methods are described in detail in references [3], [4]. The architectures of the evaluated DL neural networks (U-Net, PM-Net, CAE, and CAED, top to bottom) are described in Table I. They follow the original model structures but are tailored to the shape of the particular input data. For all models, the Dropout and LeakyReLU coefficients are both equal to 0.3, while the kerne size is $(2, 2, 2)$.

The REM reconstruction task can be expressed as solving the minimum RMSE problem for the function $p_w(\cdot)$ that denotes the interpolation method, which reconstructs the REM [10]:

$$\underset{\mathbf{w}}{\text{minimize}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left\| \epsilon_n \left(\tilde{\Psi}_n - p_w(\Psi_n) \right) \right\|_F^2}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{w} := \{w_1, \dots, w_{N_w}\}$ represents the collection of the weights of all layers in the NN, N_w in total, N is the number of input examples, ϵ is the error metric, $\tilde{\Psi}_n$ is the estimated REM, and $\|\cdot\|_F$ expresses a Frobenius norm. It is important to note that in order to obtain a uniform range of the RMSE across the non-normalized and normalized data and the statistical and DL methods, the error is computed on the original and estimated values of the REM in dB, and the result is in the same metric.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF THE FOUR DL NEURAL NETWORKS' ARCHITECTURES.

Layer Type	N_f /Stride/Size
U-Net model: [7]	
<i>Encoder Part:</i>	
$C_1 := \text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	32/(1, 1, 1)/-
$C_2 := \text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	32/(1, 2, 2)/-
$C_3 := \text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	64/(2, 3, 3)/-
$C_4 := \text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	128/(1, 1, 1)/-
$C_B := \text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	128/(2, 2, 2)/-
<i>Decoder Part:</i>	
$U_1 := \text{UpSampling3D}$	-/(1, 2, 2)
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[U_1; C_4]$	-/-
$DC_1 := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU} + \text{Dropout}$	256/(1, 1, 1)
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[DC_1; C_3]$	-/-
$DC_2 := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU} + \text{Dropout}$	128/(2, 3, 3)
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[DC_2; C_2]$	-/-
$DC_3 := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU} + \text{Dropout}$	32/(1, 2, 2)
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[DC_3; C_1]$	-/-
$DC_3 := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU} + \text{Dropout}$	32/(1, 1, 1)
$C_5 := \text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	1/(1, 1, 1)/-
PM-Net model: [9]	
<i>Encoder Part:</i>	
AveragePooling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)/-
$C_{1-3} := [\text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}] \times 3$	32/(1, 1, 1)/-
AveragePooling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)/-
$C_4 := \text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	16/(1, 1, 1)/-
AveragePooling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)/-
$C_5 := \text{Atrous Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$ (dilation 4)	8/(1, 1, 1)
$C_6 := \text{Atrous Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}$ (dilation 2)	4/(1, 1, 1)
<i>Decoder Part:</i>	
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[C_6; C_4]$	-/-
$DC_1 := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU}$	16/(1, 1, 1)/-
$U_1 := \text{UpSampling3D}$	-/(2, 2, 2)
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[U_1; C_3]$	-/-
$C_n := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU} \times 2$	32/(1, 1, 1)/-
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[DC_2; C_2]$	-/-
$DC_3 := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU} \times 2$	32/(1, 1, 1)/-
$C_n := \text{Concatenate}[DC_3; C_1]$	-/-
$DC_4 := \text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU} \times 2$	32/(1, 1, 1)/-
$U_2 := \text{UpSampling3D}$	-/(2, 2, 2)
CAE model: [5]	
$[\text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}] \times 3$	1, 32, 32/(1, 1, 1)/-
AveragePooling3D	-/(2, 3, 3)/-
$[\text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU} \rightarrow \text{AveragePooling3D}] \times 3$	32, 32, 32/1/(2, 2, 2)
$[\text{Conv3D} + \text{LeakyReLU}] \times 3$	32, 32, 32/1/-
AveragePooling3D	-/(1, 2, 2)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	16/1/-
Conv3DTranspose + LeakyReLU	16/1/-
UpSampling3D	-/(1, 2, 2)
$[\text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU}] \times 3$	32, 32, 32/1/-
UpSampling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)
$[\text{Conv3DTranspose} + \text{LeakyReLU}] \times 3$	32, 32, 32/1/-
Conv3DTranspose + LeakyReLU	32/1/-
CAED model: [10]	
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	4/(1, 1, 1)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	1/(2, 2, 2)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	3/(1, 1, 1)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	16/(2, 2, 2)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	9/(1, 1, 1)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	8/(1, 1, 1)/-
AveragePooling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	9/(1, 1, 1)/-
UpSampling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)
Conv3DTranspose + LeakyReLU	9/(1, 1, 1)/-
UpSampling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)
Conv3DTranspose + LeakyReLU	5/(1, 1, 1)/-
Conv3DTranspose + LeakyReLU	3/(1, 1, 1)/-
UpSampling3D	-/(2, 2, 2)
Conv3DTranspose + LeakyReLU	3/(1, 1, 1)/-
Conv3DTranspose + LeakyReLU	11/(1, 1, 1)/-
Conv3D + LeakyReLU	1/(1, 1, 1)/-

A. Description of the Datasets

Three types of datasets, which follow the same grid structure of $M_x \times M_y \times M_z$ described in Section II-1 are used for training and testing of the evaluated models.

- **Generated Dataset** - the method and ray-tracing (RT) source data from [10] are used to generate N 3D REM examples. This is done by selecting $M_x \times M_y$ samples, starting from the bottom-left corner, its location indices being chosen at random within the area between the points (0, 0) and $(246 - M_x, 244 - M_y)$, forming M_z 2D grids, with 246×244 (which corresponds to 700×700 m) being the grid of the source data. The resulting 2D grids are stacked together into 3D maps, and this procedure is repeated N times to generate the complete dataset.
- **Simulated Dataset** - it is comprised by N REMs generated via simulation [13] of an aerial BS that takes RSS measurements from randomly moving UEs at a set of locations in a grid of $M_x \times M_y \times M_z$ elements. The RSS measurement r_l at a location l is denoted as the sum of the uplink transmit powers of all N_{UE} UEs:

$$r_l = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} h_a P_{T,UE_i} + P_0, \quad (3)$$

where l denotes the coordinates (i, j, k) , h_a is the path loss (PL) coefficient, P_0 is the noise power, and P_{T,UE_i} is the UE's uplink transmission power. The modified two ray PL model [14] is utilized to describe the channel between the UAV and the ground nodes as it considers the dominant and surface-reflected components but under the condition of the ABS operating at low altitudes, i.e. its height H_a is lower than 30 m. The channel coefficient h_a (in dB) is described as:

$$h_a = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi}{F_c} \right) - 10\gamma(H_a) \log_{10} \left| \frac{G_l(H_a)}{l} - \frac{G_r(H_a)}{r_1 + r_2} \right|, \quad (4)$$

$$l = d \sqrt{1 + \frac{(H_T - H_R)^2}{d^2}}, \quad r_1 = \sqrt{H_T^2 + \frac{(d * H_T)^2}{(H_T + H_R)^2}},$$

$$r_2 = \sqrt{H_R^2 + \left(d - \frac{d * H_T}{(H_T + H_R)} \right)^2},$$

where $F_c = 2$ GHz is the central frequency, $d = \sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2 + d_z^2}$ is the three-dimensional distance with d_x , d_y and d_z being the distances between the transmitter and the receiver in the x , y and z axes, H_T and H_R are the heights of the transmitter and the receiver, respectively, $G_l(H_a) = 15$ is the direct path coefficient, $G_r(H_a) = 5$ describe the reflected path, while $\gamma(H_a) = 3.5$ - the height-dependent propagation.

- **Real-World REMs** - This dataset is comprised of two subsets of measurement samples, which were procured

in an indoor and an outdoor environment, described in [10]. Only a general description of the experiments and environments is presented here for brevity.

The indoor RW measurements is realized in a large vicinity that includes an Automatic Positioning Tool (APT), controlled by a host computer, which collects the measurements through an SDR sensor, with four SDRs, placed on a table below the APT, transmitting Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi) signals continuously. The APT covers an area with dimensions of $6 \times 2 \times 0.75$ m as makes measurements on specific locations along the ordinate and abscissa axes for four levels of elevation - 0, 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 m above the surface of the table. The mean value of the measured samples at each location in space defines its RSS.

The outdoor RW measurements scenario uses three "sensed" UAVs that are the transmitter sources, and a separate "sensor UAV", which performs the measurements through its on-board SDR. The sensor UAV covers a pre-determined trajectory that is comprised of 40 locations (encompassing the dimensions of 105×38 m) at four altitude levels (80, 90, 100, and 110 m above sea level). The sensed UAVs fly in a realistic constellation at altitudes 10 m above that of the sensor UAV for each level. After the two sets of spatial 3D measurement samples were collected, they are used to construct tensor examples of shape $M_x \times M_y \times M_z$, through Kriging interpolation.

III. RESULTS

This Section introduces the statistical and DL methods evaluation for the three testing datasets in non-normalized and normalized format. The RMSE curves for all statistical methods and the three datasets in the cases of non-normalized and normalized data are illustrated in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively. There are several notable characteristics, namely, that for all datasets the Linear interpolation shows the worst results, with improvement achieved by the NN method, while the best results are obtained by the IDW and Kriging, with the latter being only slightly better despite its much greater computational complexity. This tendency is retained when the data is normalized (Fig. 2). In the case of non-normalized values (Fig. 1), each dataset has specific range of error within the span of several dB, with the best accuracy reached for the RW measurements dataset. It is also characterized with the smallest variance (within 2-3 dB) in the performance of the interpolation methods. At $\rho = 10\%$, the generated, simulated and RW measurements datasets have minimum RMSE of 16, 11, and 4 dB, respectively. As observed in Fig. 2, the RMSE have been reduced significantly (between 9 and 16 dB) for all methods and datasets, with those achieving the largest RMSE, also exhibiting the greatest increase in accuracy. Additionally, there is a greater variation in the RMSE between the Linear and Kriging methods as ρ increases.

When it comes to the DL methods and non-normalized data (Fig. 3), the generated dataset exhibits the largest RMSE, with an improvement for the simulated dataset, while the best

results are obtained for the RW measurements. The RMSE for the DL methods do not follow similar distribution as is the case for the statistical methods. Notably, the CAED method exhibits very small variation with the increase of ρ , particularly for the RW measurement dataset. In contrast, the CAE method is characterized with a much more significant decline of the error apart from the case of the RW measurements, reaching the best accuracy across all datasets. As for the U-Net, in spite of the much greater number of parameters, it does not provide a significant gain compared to the PM-Net. In fact, the latter achieves about 1 dB better accuracy. Thus, the enhanced field of view of the model's filters enabled by the dilation, provides both lower training complexity and improved RMSE. At $\rho = 10\%$, the generated, simulated and RW measurements datasets have minimum RMSE of 13, 8, and 6.84 dB, respectively. Overall, the best results are achieved for the CAE and CAED models. As for the normalized samples case (Fig. 4), it is evident that the results for the three dataset types, all vary within a similar range. Just as in the case for the statistical methods, the RMSE decreases with the difference being about 21, 16, and 11 dB ($\rho = 10\%$) for the generated, simulated and RW measurements datasets. Additionally, there are some differences in the models' performance curve, in contrast to the results for non-normalized data. For the generated dataset, CAED achieves the lowest RMSE, while for the simulated dataset, CAE is the most effective. It is notable that even though the CAE and CAED models exhibit the highest accuracy for low ρ , the resulting RMSE does not vary significantly with ρ , which may be due to overfitting.

Fig. 1. RMSE for all statistical methods and the three datasets (non-normalized value samples).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper evaluated several widely-used statistical and DL methods for 3D REM reconstruction for three dataset types (generated, simulation-based, and real-world measurements) for both absolute value and normalized samples, to determine the impact of normalization on the accuracy. RMSE of as low as -8 dB is achieved for sampling ratio of 10% using the

Fig. 2. RMSE for all statistical methods (normalized value samples). (a) Generated dataset. (b) Simulated dataset. (c) RWM dataset.

CAED DL method. The results establish that normalized RSS data improve the accuracy for applications that do not require prediction of the exact RSS values, such as identifying areas with under-utilized spectrum for aerial base station (ABS) placement. Future work will include evaluating of the capacity gains for UAV-assisted networks with CAED based ABS positioning.

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Fig. 3. RMSE for all DL methods (absolute value samples). (a) Generated dataset. (b) Simulated dataset. (c) RWM dataset (U-Net and PM-Net). (d) RWM dataset (CAE). (e) RWM dataset (CAED).

Fig. 4. RMSE for all DL methods (normalized value samples). (a) Generated dataset (U-Net, PM-Net, CAED). (b) Generated dataset (CAE). (c) Simulated dataset (U-Net, PM-Net, CAED). (d) Simulated dataset (CAE). (e) RWM dataset (U-Net and PM-Net). (f) RWM dataset (CAE). (g) RWM dataset (CAED).